

ARTYKUŁY PRZEGLĄDOWE I RECENZJE

DOI: 10.15805/ap2022.1.04

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THEORETICAL APPROACHES TOWARDS SOFT REPRESSIONS AND SOCIAL MOBILIZATION: LESSONS LEARNT FROM ASIAN AND REGIONAL STUDIES³

Introduction

In common understanding, soft repressions are not always considered a powerful tool for influencing social mobilization because they do not violate protesters' bodily integrity and are sometimes perceived as not severe⁴. Nevertheless, according to Charles Tilly's definition of repression, they are a kind of action that increases the cost of the public activity of a collective actor, usually a social movement⁵. As such, social repressions cannot be ignored in studies that aim to account for the dynamics of social mobilization across the world⁶. Various entities, both state

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³ This research paper is a result of the research project Civil Disorder in Pandemic-ridden European Union. It was financially supported by the National Science Centre, Poland [grant number 2021/43/B/HS5/00290].

⁴ Oscar J. M. García, *Soft Repression and the Current Wave of Social Mobilisations in Spain*, „Social Movement Studies”, 25 November 2013, pp. 303–308.

⁵ Charles Tilly, *From Mobilization to Revolution*, McGraw-Hill College, New York 1978.

⁶ Lasse Lindekilde, *Soft Repression and Mobilization: The Case of Transnational Activism of Danish Muslims During the Cartoons Controversy*, „International Journal of Middle East Studies”, 15 July 2010, pp. 451–469.

and private, use soft repressions depending on the region under study. Instead of physical force, they draw upon mental violence⁷. Scholarship on such forms of repression is increasingly important since it allows students of contentious politics to comprehend the dynamics of contention. Additionally, going beyond a traditional understanding of police-driven repression, it offers a more complex insight into the nature of contemporary repression⁸. It broadens the traditional approach to repression as a hard repression⁹. In contrast to the common understanding, recent studies reveal that soft repression can be an extremely powerful weapon for fighting dissidents¹⁰. Moreover, in the 21st century, with the development of society and technology, new ways to implement this form of repression emerge and boost its impact¹¹. Among other things, thanks to advanced technology, such as using computer bots, political actors can apply soft repressions using the most popular social networking sites, both for a group and a specific person on a large scale¹². Their analysis has considerably contributed to developing our knowledge of how the plethora of political actors influence social mobilization with non-violent means¹³.

Soft repression plays a special role in the repertoire of repression. As Jan Jämte and Rune Ellefsen argue, the consequences of soft repression are most evident at the individual level when there is an imposition of self-control on activists. That, in turn, leads to the demobilization of the movement and makes it challenging to continue mobilizing against governments¹⁴. Importantly, a similar view is presented

⁷ David Stoesz, *Human Service Cartels: The Soft Repression of the Mediocracy*, „Research on Social Work Practice”, 16 December 2020, pp. 687–702.

⁸ Téwodros W. Workneh, *From State Repression to Fear of Non-state Actors: Examining Emerging Threats of Journalism Practice in Ethiopia*, „Journalism Practice”, 3 May 2021, pp. 1–18.

⁹ Donatella della Porta, *On Violence and Repression: A Relational Approach*, „Government and Opposition”, 1 April 2014, pp. 159–187.

¹⁰ Dag Tanneberg, Christoph Stefes, Wolfgang Merkel, *Hard Times and Regime Failure: Autocratic Responses to Economic Downturns*, „Contemporary Politics”, 1 March 2013, pp. 115–129. See also: Luis Fernandez, *Policing Dissent: Social Control and the Anti-Globalization Movement*, Rutgers University Press, New Brunswick, New Jersey 2008; Jules Boykoff, *Limiting Dissent: The Mechanisms of State Repression in the USA*, „Social Movement Studies”, 26 November 2007, pp. 281–310.

¹¹ Anette Linden, Bert Klandermans, *Stigmatisation and Repression of Extreme-right Activism in the Netherlands*, „Mobilization: An International Quarterly”, 1 June 2006, pp. 213–228.

¹² Hadi Sohrabi, *New Media, Contentious Politics, and Political Public Sphere in Iran*, „Critical Arts”, 17 February 2021, pp. 35–48; Jennifer Earl, Thomas V. Maher, and Jennifer Pan, *The Digital Repression of Social Movements, Protest, and Activism: A Synthetic Review*, „Science Advances”, 9 March 2022.

¹³ See, e.g., Steven Feldstein, *The Rise of Digital Repression: How Technology is Reshaping Power, Politics, and Resistance*, Oxford University Press, New York 2021.

¹⁴ Jan Jämte, Rune Ellefsen, *The Consequences of Soft Repression*, „Mobilization: An International Quarterly”, 1 September 2020, pp. 383–404.

by other students of soft repression who delve analytically into the attempts to control protests, restricting or influencing activists without the use of force¹⁵.

Note should be taken that one of the pillars of nondemocratic political regimes' stability is the use of repression¹⁶. Asian states have a long history and the resulting experience of stabilizing their autocratic political regimes¹⁷. It is a history of using various forms of hard and soft repression to neutralize the threat of autocracy's collapse. However, it is also a history of social reactions to repression. Thus, relationships between the rulers and the ruled in Asia constitute a promising laboratory for social scientists¹⁸. Unsurprisingly, empirical observations of these relationships are the rich basis for generalization and theorization for the most important works in the studies on contentious politics¹⁹.

This review article aims to introduce a critical discussion with selected theoretical approaches used to study soft repressions and their impact on the dynamics of social mobilization and demobilization. Engaging with the recent studies on soft repressions, it draws on lessons learnt from Asian and regional studies. It argues that the extent of their application to understanding contentious politics goes beyond single case studies. Although some studies are context-driven, they can be modified or used as offered to explore and account for the relationships between factors in studies of different context-based single cases and comparative studies. At the same time, the scope of exploration is not limited to Asia or any particular region.

The remainder of the article consists of five parts. The first four parts present and analyze critically theoretical approaches treating soft repressions as an explaining

¹⁵ Jennifer Earl, *Tanks, Tear Gas, and Taxes: Toward a Theory of Movement Repression*, „Sociological Theory”, 1 January 2003, p. 46

¹⁶ Johannes Gerschewski, *The Three Pillars of Stability: Legitimation, Repression, and Co-optation in Autocratic Regimes*, „Democratization”, 29 January 2013, pp. 13–38. See also: Maria Josua, Mirjam Edel, *To Repress or Not to Repress — Regime Survival Strategies in the Arab Spring*, „Terrorism and Political Violence”, 12 March 2014, pp. 289–309.

¹⁷ Xu Xu, *To Repress or to Co-opt? Authoritarian Control in the Age of Digital Surveillance*, „American Journal of Political Science”, 7 April 2020, pp. 309–325.

¹⁸ Rui Hou, *Maintaining Social Stability Without Solving Problems: Emotional Repression in the Chinese Petition System*, „The China Quarterly”, 17 December 2020, pp. 635–654. See also: Hsin-Hsien Wang, Wei-Feng Tzeng, Shinn-Shyr Wang, Wei-Chih Chiu, *A King Stifling Voices of Dissent? Popular Protests and State Responses in Xi's China*, „Pacific Focus”, 15 April 2021, pp. 92–115.

¹⁹ See, e.g., Christian Davenport (ed.), *Paths to State Repression: Human Rights Violations and Contentious Politics*, Rowman & Littlefield, New York 2000; Ming-Sho Ho, Wai Ki Wan, *Universities as an Arena of Contentious Politics: Mobilization and Control in Hong Kong's Anti-Extradition Movement of 2019*, „International Studies in Sociology of Education”, 25 November 2021, pp. 1–24; Cai Yongshun, *Power Structure and Regime Resilience: Contentious Politics in China*, „British Journal of Political Science”, 13 May 2008, pp. 411–432; Carwyn Morris, *Digital Displacement: The Spatialities of Contentious Politics in China's Digital Territory*, „Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers”, 16 June 2022, pp. 1075–1089.

variable of de(mobilization). The focus is on the most influential approaches in recent years that gained the highest impact on the development of studies on contentious politics measured by the number of citations (more than ten citations on Google Scholar) and whose analytical efficiency has been confirmed with empirical evidence gathered by at least two independent scholars or research groups. Some researchers challenge this Web search engine as not the most respected scholarly source of knowledge and consider the h-Index or Impact Factor of a paper the more respected academic indicator²⁰. However, the article focuses on something other than the highest-quality frameworks and therefore sticks to Google Scholar. Accordingly, it is devoted to the most influential ones, and their quality is under the article's substantive consideration. The review's goal underlies the choice. The article finishes with a discussion of avenues for future research on analytical tools useful to study soft repression.

Myra Max Ferree's Typology of Soft Repression

In "Soft Repression: Ridicule, Stigma, and Silencing in Gender-Based Movements", Myra Max Ferree offered the most influential typology of soft repressions often considered a starting point for differentiating between various forms of soft repression and accounting for their social consequences²¹. As Ferree argues, nowadays, social movements only sometimes strive to impact the ruling elite and coup at the level of state authorities. In an increasing number of protests, protesters are more concerned with changing the view of civil society than with total rebellion and overthrowing the government. More and more protests are directed at civil society, not the state²². Ferree observes that it translates into the pluralization of actors using repressions against the participants of social movements, as well as the development of the repertoire of repression. The interests of non-state actors are increasingly threatened, which fuels violent relationships between them and social movements.

²⁰ Alexander Serenko, John Dumay, *Citation Classics Published in Knowledge Management Journals. Part II: Studying Research Trends and Discovering the Google Scholar Effect*, „Journal of Knowledge Management”, 1 October 2015, pp. 1335–1355; José Van Dijck, *Search Engines and the Production of Academic Knowledge*, „International Journal of Cultural Studies”, 26 November 2010, pp. 574–592.

²¹ Myra M. Ferree, *Soft Repression: Ridicule, Stigma, and Silencing in Gender-Based Movements*, in: *Authority in Contention: Research in Social Movements, Conflicts and Change*, Daniel J. Myers, Daniel M. Cress (eds.), Emerald Insight, Bingley 2004, pp. 85–101.

²² See also: Narzanin Massoumi, *The Role of Civil Society in Political Repression: The UK Prevent Counter-Terrorism Programme*, „Sociology”, 2 April 2021, pp. 959–977.

Accordingly, Ferree distinguishes between two theoretical categories that describe repression employed by state and non-state actors. The first one, hard repression, is a classic category often referred to as protest policing²³. It is the state-driven mobilization of force to control or destroy opposition activities through the use or threat of violence. In turn, the category of soft repression covers the mobilization of means to silence or root out opposition ideas through mental violence. The latter is characterized by the lack of threats to use force and the very force. Nevertheless, Ferree proposed a descriptive approach towards the nature of soft repression. Its operationalizable definition can be inferred from numerous examples rather than directly formulated.

Ferree assumes that political subjects use soft repression in the often-overlapping forms of ridicule, stigma, and silencing corresponding to micro-, meso-, and macrolevels of analysis. At the micro-level, soft repression that takes the form of ridicule is directed at individuals and groups. Ridicule is oriented to diminish or disarm the repressed. It draws upon employing unkind words to create an image of the repressed. It results in making a person look stupid, mocking, and intimidated²⁴. Identifying ridicule in discourse can be difficult due to the need-to-know various cultural codes. Moreover, it may also depend on political views.

Stigma is peculiar to an impaired collective identity. At the meso-level of stigma, it is a link between the stigmatized and a group that leads to discrediting and devaluation of how the group is depicted. Resting on real quality, the repressing actor constructs stigma by showing a person's quality or behaviour as evidence that the person is worse than others, i.e., defective. The challenged quality can be held voluntarily (e.g., putting on clothes that refer to a collective identity) or involuntarily (e.g., race). The repressing actor changes the quality into a stigma implying that the person is morally flawed and to be eschewed. Stigma is socially constructed to determine the perception of the repressed in their social environment as inferior²⁵. As Ferree emphasizes, stigmatizing is used against social movements which have already built credibility in civil society. It aims to stop its further development and minimize gains by increasing the cost of identification with the group²⁶.

At the macro-level, ridicule and stigma can accumulate to produce silence. Nonetheless, silence can also be generated by excluding social movements from

²³ Jennifer Earl, *Political Repression: Iron Fists, Velvet Gloves, and Diffuse Control*, „*Annual Review of Sociology*”, 16 July 2011, pp. 261–284; Jennifer Earl, Sarah A. Soule, *Seeing Blue: A Police-centered Explanation of Protest Policing*, „*Mobilization: An International Quarterly*”, 4 August 2006, pp. 145–164; Jennifer Earl, Sarah A. Soule, John D. McCarthy, *Protest Under Fire? Explaining the Policing of Protest*, „*American Sociological Review*”, 1 August 2003, pp. 581–606.

²⁴ Myra. M. Ferree, op. cit., p. 90.

²⁵ Ibidem, p. 92.

²⁶ Ibidem.

having a voice in the mass media. By withdrawing attention from movement mobilization, the mass media can reduce it as the repressing actors. At the same time, providing media coverage of protests does not mean giving a voice since it may exclude the frames that make sense of a social movement's activity. In contrast to the types mentioned above of soft repression, Ferree introduces the subtypes of silencing. Accordingly, silencing includes ignoring a social movement's existence and blocking its perspectives²⁷.

On the one hand, this typology provides a universal theoretical tool to differentiate between the three major types of soft repression. It is helpful to explore how non-state actors discourage activists from engaging in protests by increasing the social cost of their engagement. On the other hand, to a lower extent, the typology applies to scrutinizing soft repression used by state actors in democratic structures since they have to avoid ridiculing political opponents to maintain substantive deliberation in public discourse. Therefore, the typology is worth developing.

Moreover, Ferree does not take into account repression imposed in the form of regulation by the state on social movements, which is also a form of soft repression. Therefore, when applying this typology to anti-government movements, one should consider expanding it to include types that only state actors can use. Such repression can appear under the name of channelling. It is a form of not using coercion but nevertheless influencing social mobilization with the help of regulations applying a kind of pressure²⁸. Among other things, hindering the financing of organizations or access to public places work as state-driven soft repressions.

Finally, while the typology goes into details of silencing, it remains silent about the types of stigmatization and ridicule. As such, it does not allow researchers to differ systematically between the subtypes of particular kinds of soft repression. Therefore, it is worth extending this typology to include a variety of the identified forms of soft repression, e.g., by doing extensive empirical research on the discursive delegitimization of a powerful social movement.

²⁷ Ibidem, pp. 94–96.

²⁸ Oscar J. M. García, op. cit. See also: Julien Talpin, *Why French Racial Minorities Do Not Mobilize More Often. Disempowerment, Tactical Repertoires and Soft Repression of Antiracist Movements*, „Ethnic and Racial Studies”, 1 February 2022, pp. 1–22.

Soft Repression and Its Consequences in Jan Jämte and Rune Ellefsen's Theoretical Framework

In "The Consequences of Soft Repression", Jämte and Ellefsen focus on soft repression as an explaining variable. However, they also delve into its theoretical variants. Namely, they reflect on what consequences come with the use of these repressions and what are the experiences of people against whom such repression has been used. As the authors argue, nowadays, unconventional methods of repressing protesters are used more and more often to direct protests in a different direction, influence public opinion about protesters or demobilize them through the use of diverse forms of soft repression. The authors rest on the definition of soft repression proposed by Jennifer Earl as one that is exerted through subtler techniques than coercion and the threat or use of violence²⁹. Jämte and Ellefsen introduce two types of soft repression, i.e., stigmatization and labelling, and point out that soft repression is employed not only in civil society and the media environment. Instead, it can be a potent weapon in the hands of governments³⁰. Jämte and Ellefsen avoid referring to ridicule that is rarely used in democratic structures. They also omit silencing that causes difficulties during coding, especially when researchers do not know the context very well. However, Jämte and Ellefsen do not exclude the possibility that ridicule and silencing may emerge as the consequences of stigmatization and labelling. Unlike Ferree, they avoid including them in the repertoire of soft repression.

According to Jämte and Ellefsen, labelling is a kind of attribution of a particular name, word, or association to a given individual or group. This label aims to cause the community to doubt the value of a specific group or person and even spark negative emotion-driven reactions in society³¹. Through such a treatment applied to a group or person, a part of society may turn away from it and not want to be a part of it. It reduces the efficiency of potential calls for action and decreases the possibility of gaining new and maintaining current movement participants.

Stigmatization has already been described in the above analysis of Ferree's approach. Similarly, Jämte and Ellefsen's model involves discrediting and devaluing a group by portraying a trait seen as a defect. This trait can be acquired or innate. However, the important thing is to show it as harmful or socially unacceptable to construct a stigma. Jämte and Ellefsen avoid discussing the state administrative sanctions or silencing as repression. However, as they argue, they may be the consequences of soft repressions rather than the very repressions. State administrative

²⁹ J. Jämte, R. Ellefsen, *op. cit.*, p. 385.

³⁰ *Ibidem.*

³¹ *Ibidem.*, p. 394.

sanctions involve a kind of exclusion from the society of groups characterized by a particular trait or name. It is done, among other things, by restricting access to public places where they could promote their activities. Silencing is presented at the individual level as self-control or self-silencing, which is the result of labelling or stigmatization³². However, Jämte and Ellefsen also consider silencing in classical terms, such as limited access to media coverage. At the same time, it is also a consequence rather than a form of soft repression.

The typology formulated by Jämte and Ellefsen applies to study the possible consequences of soft repression but offers blurred relationships between the individual categories. It omits to discuss under what conditions relationships between stigmatization/labelling and silencing/ridicule/regulations emerge. Although the researchers presented consequences of repression that could function independently as a type of repression, they did not include them in the typology as separate elements. The theoretical approach offered by Jämte and Ellefsen is an essential theoretical tool for research on social movements as long as it allows for identifying the meaningful frames in a discourse aimed at social mobilization. Nevertheless, it is still worth developing theoretical links between the categories.

Soft and Hard Repression as the Most Effective Means of Suppressing Protests: The Case Study of Hong Kong 2020

Another theoretical perspective that strongly focuses on soft repression has been offered in an article entitled “Beijing’s Hard and Soft Repression in Hong Kong” by Victoria Tin-bor Hui. The author describes the means of classic repression used by the rulers during the 2020 Hong Kong protests and pays special attention to Beijing that used unconventional means of repression, which are soft repressions. In this case, soft repression manifests itself in a completely different way than in the previously discussed approaches, namely centred around legal aspects. They are not directly named in Tin-bor Hui’s text in any way but based on the examples. Nonetheless, it is possible to identify their essence by delving analytically into these examples.

Stigmatization can be taken as the most classic form of soft repression described by Tin-bor Hui. The stigmatized group, here medics (medical students and doctors), fulfil Ferree’s essential criteria included in a definition of a group that enjoys credibility in civil society³³. However, when pressed and slowly excluded from society,

³² Ibidem.

³³ Victoria Tin-bor Hui, *Beijing’s Hard and Soft Repression in Hong Kong*, „Orbis”, 1 February 2020, p. 299.

it can lose its appeal to other citizens who are part of this group. Citizens may fear further or other repressions from contacting or being part of the stigmatized group.

The forms of soft repression, which have not been named explicitly but occurred and definitively affected the cost of the protest (i.e., the consequences of protest participation for protesters' everyday life), include filling important positions with people with connotations to those in power, limiting public funding to specific establishments, or restricting the ability of protesters to assemble legally. This type of repression is called channelling in the subject literature, which is often understood as a regulation. Nevertheless, as Anthony Oberschall and Charles Tilly argue, the present regulation should be considered a less virulent, although no less effective, form of repression³⁴. It means that another approach confirms the possibility of repressing citizens through legal means available to the state actors to influence social mobilization. While pointing out that this also constitutes a form of repression, although less acute, it still leads to achieving the goals.

Non-state actors who own various types of business premises where speeches or attempts at mobilization could occur can also apply some of such regulations because, as managers of their property, they can restrict selected citizens or social movements from using them. Nevertheless, it has a relatively small share in repressions if we compare it to the scale of the state-imposed restrictions. Therefore, special attention should be paid to legal regulations that can exclude particular movements from public life and affect the equal use of facilities.

In addition, silencing has reappeared in two forms: a consequence and a means of repression. In the former situation, it can be used for silencing social movements. Due to the emerging fear associated with the possibility of losing resources, the repressing actors make use of silencing. It also occurs in the classic form at the macro level, restricting the ability to communicate one's demands, including through the mass media.

The forms of soft repression indicated by Tin-bor Hui include the means available to those in power and show the repression of protesters through soft means by state actors. In Hongkong, the use of a combination of classic and soft repression was aimed at demobilizing protesters by attacking from both sides, directly and indirectly. The state actor, using the combination of soft and hard repression, succeeded in discouraging others trying to join and support protesters, such as lawyers, and journalists, from protesting³⁵. Tin-bor Hui has yet to propose a new typology that could help establish the configuration of hard and soft repression forms but confirms the presence of the previously mentioned elements and shows other forms that soft repression can take. However, Tin-bor Hui delivers an example of

³⁴ Charles Tilly, *op. cit.*

³⁵ *Ibidem.*

the efficient use of these two types of repression to trigger social demobilization. It determines a promising starting point for further research.

Tin-bor Hui's approach avoids introducing a specific typology of soft repression used against protesters in Hong Kong. Such a typology would be helpful to map more and less efficient repressions used to spark demobilization. Nevertheless, it does not exclude its applicability after modification and extraction from the description of the specific types used by those in power.

Relational Repression as a Form of Soft Repression in China

In "Relational Repression in China: Using Social Ties to Demobilize Protesters", Yanhua Deng and Kevin J. O'Brien researched soft repression in China. According to the authors, in recent times, researchers have focused too much on classic repression, ignoring the impact of these theoretically softer repressions on the dynamics of protestors' mobilization³⁶. Deng and O'Brien noted that although researchers try to balance the research on repression, they still concentrate on forms of soft repression such as surveillance or the ridicule and stigmatization mentioned by Ferree. They proposed a new line of research on relational repression. As they argued, in some cases, soft repression was effective in demobilizing protesters. However, if the state actors do not ultimately end the protest and do not demobilize protesters, they can influence its scope and length while leaving room for negotiation between protesters and local authorities.

Deng and O'Brien provided a definition of relational repression, which is a control technique that uses social ties to demobilize protesters³⁷. This repression is characterized by persuasion, influence on individuals, and pressure on protesters by people known to be individual protesters. Relational repression is based on a network of connections and relationships and uses interpersonal ties. It relies on the creation of pressure by society on activists to ultimately demobilize them. Despite the lack of use of physical coercion, a kind of psychological coercion and even emotional blackmail can be observed. This repression is used on its own and in combination with classic methods of repressing citizens.

Relational repression consists of four consecutive stages: (1) Gathering information on the connections between those participating in the protest and those who can influence them; (2) People connected to the activists are recruited into work teams; (3) Members of the work teams are organized and deployed to demobilize

³⁶ Yanhua Deng, Kevin J. O'Brien, *Relational Repression in China: Using Social Ties to Demobilize Protesters*, „The China Quarterly”, 1 August 2013, p. 534.

³⁷ Ibidem.

the protesters; (4) Team members are mobilized to take their task seriously and intimidated about the cost of failure, those who are not sufficiently motivated to do their job are disciplined³⁸.

The point of relational repression is to influence the other person through emotional blackmail, pressure, or inducement using emotions. Therefore, close relationships are the most useful here. Nevertheless, if such ties are lacking among employees in work teams, further connections are used³⁹. Work team employees are strongly motivated by intimidation and the threat of consequences for not fulfilling their duties. Penalties for non-compliance in work teams are so severe that many times, despite ties with relatives, work team employees are determined to persuade activists to end their engagement in protest.

This model of soft repression can be effective to extinguish protests. However, the lack of connections between labour teams and protesters can be a significant obstacle to influencing activists. They may not have enough third-party motivation or influence to give up protesting due to the lack of strong interpersonal ties between those persuading them to end their protests and those being persuaded. Moreover, in a democratic state, it is doubtful that forming such teams is possible, but it is not impossible. Therefore, one should assume the possibility that those in power may attempt to create such working teams. Finally, the effectiveness of relational repression depends not only on how much influence the state has over the work team members but also on how strong the ties between the protesters and these workers are. Therefore, the effectiveness of relational repression should depend on these two factors.

As such, Deng and O'Brien provide an efficient exploratory and explanatory framework to delve analytically into the mechanism and consequences of specific soft repression in selected contexts. Its scope is relatively narrow, so applying this theoretical approach in combination with other models may be helpful, depending on analytical needs, especially research goals, and questions.

Conclusions

The four models under discussion result from Asian and regional studies. They include elements of soft repression and present illustrative examples of its use against citizens by non-state and state actors. Although they apply to analyze soft repression to a great extent, their applicability differs across individual research goals and country-specific contexts. In the classic typology presented by Ferree,

³⁸ Ibidem, p. 537.

³⁹ Ibidem, p. 544.

which consists of ridicule, stigmatization, and silencing, one should allow for the possibility that individual repressions are applied at other levels. Among other things, silencing appeared to Ferree at the macro level of analysis. Still, research by Jämte and Ellefsen revealed that it could also occur in another form at the micro level of analysis. Thus, the use of particular types of repression at levels other than those presented should not be ruled out, as the subsequent studies uncovered. They also exposed a tremendous need for further theorizing of the links between the models' components and defining the conditions under which the causal relations between soft repression forms and demobilization emerge. Simultaneously, they paved the way for future research that would deliver further empirical observations to boost our understanding of soft repression forms at different social levels.

Moreover, Ferree's model lacks soft repression that state actors in the form of regulations can only apply. In contrast to Ferree's approach, Jämte and Ellefsen draw scholarly attention primarily to the consequences of soft repressions, focusing on labelling and stigmatization. Nevertheless, some of the results can be repressions themselves, as evidenced by showing silencing as a consequence of using labelling. The situation is similar to administrative sanctions, which can also manifest themselves in the form of denial of funding for projects inconsistent with the views of those with the resources, as was the case in Hong Kong, where universities supporting the strikes were threatened with withholding of funding. As Deng and O'Brian emphasize, its use can effectively demobilize protesters by exploiting social or family ties.

However, problems arise with accounting for this repression, such as gaining knowledge of a lack of connections to individuals or a low commitment to the relationships in question. If there are no strong ties between protesters and members of the work team and strong state influence over the work team, this repression does not show its usefulness in meeting the repressing's interest. It may be challenging for researchers to acquire the primary data necessary and sufficient to explain those mechanisms. Furthermore, this lesson learnt from Asian studies may be essential to explore the social cost of engagement in protest activity as the consequence of repression. At the same time, beyond the Asian context, the meaning of family ties can vary. Therefore, further analytical work on the conditions under which the relationships between factors emerge is required.

Two of the four explanatory models are strongly contextualized. Some were created based on the Hong Kong and China cases, while others were rooted in regional studies. The conclusions of Asian studies were generalized to increase the models' analytical power. Nevertheless, the other works' explanatory potential significantly exceeds the understanding of soft repression in a regional context as well. They can be successfully applied to study the consequences of soft repression

in nondemocratic countries. In addition, they may become the basis for comparative research and the formulation of new theories extending beyond one region.

Last but not least, the studies under scrutiny reveal the relevance of conducting further research on soft repression and point out the elements of state involvement in using soft repression and how powerful the means are at the disposal of those in power in various state contexts. The typology presented by Ferree is the most universal but has its limitations. It should be developed with additional types of soft repression, particularly those that only the state can use, as well as the occurrence of the listed types at other stages of analysis.

Abstract

Theoretical Approaches towards Repressions and Social Mobilization

To what extent do current models apply to analyze soft repression? Research on soft repression is still under development, and due to technological advancement, it is necessary to analyze different types of soft repression in a way to modify and refine existing typologies. Drawing on lessons learnt from Asian and regional studies, this article aims to discuss critically selected theoretical tools used to study soft repression. It scrutinizes four models that apply to delve analytically into different types of soft repression. The focus is on the most influential approaches in recent years that gained the highest impact on the development of studies on contentious politics. The first typology applies to differentiate between soft repression forms used mainly by non-state actors. The second approach treats soft repression as an explaining variable, as the text focuses on the consequences of soft repression. The third model applies to studying hard and soft repression during protests. Its analysis exposes how the combination of effectively selected forms of repression leads to the demobilization of individual movements and discourages participation in the protest. The last model involves a specific form of soft repression that uses relationships and interpersonal ties to demobilize protesters.

Keywords: contentious politics, soft repression, social mobilization, theoretical category, typology